

Editorial

Malaria and Diseases Awareness

Anil Mishra, PhD

Tulane University School of Medicine, New Orleans, LA 70112

(Received December 2, 2018; Accepted December 19, 2018)

Each year, WHO estimates more than 200 million cases of malaria worldwide, with over 445,000 deaths, on which approximately 90% of deaths caused by the mosquito-borne disease occur in several under developed countries including south-east Asia, south America, and several African countries. People with malaria often experience fever, chills, and flu-like illness. If untreated, they may develop severe complications and die. . Most of the people who die from the disease are young children in Africa. Disasters from natural hazards like floods, earthquakes and landslides can cause immense suffering and have far-reaching health consequences for millions of people. Malaria signs and symptoms typically begin within a few weeks after being bitten by an infected mosquito. However, some types of malaria parasites can lie dormant in your body for up to a year. If you're traveling to locations where malaria is common, take steps to prevent mosquito bites by wearing protective clothing, using insect repellants and sleeping under treated mosquito nets. Depending on the area you are visiting and your individual risk

factors for infection, you may also want to take preventive medicine before, during and after your trip. Many malaria parasites are now resistant to the most common drugs used to treat the disease. If you're going to be traveling to a location where malaria is common, talk to your doctor a few months ahead of time about whether you should take drugs before, during and after your trip to help protect you from malaria parasites. In general, the drugs taken to prevent malaria are the same drugs used to treat the disease. Your doctor needs to know when and where you'll be traveling so that he or she can help you evaluate your risk for infection and, if necessary, prescribe the drug that will work best on the type of malaria parasite most commonly found in that region. Scientists around the world are trying to develop a safe and effective vaccine for malaria. As of yet, however, there is still no malaria vaccine approved for human use. A vaccine against malaria called RTS, S, was approved by European regulators in 2015. It is undergoing pilot trials in select countries in 2016. To further raise awareness, WHO celebrates World Malaria Day each year on 25 April

to underscore the collective energy and commitment of the global malaria community in uniting around the common goal of a world free of malaria.

In the Western Pacific Region, the theme highlights the commitment of its leaders to attain a malaria-free Asia Pacific by 2030.

Preventive Medication

There are a number of medications that can help prevent or interrupt malaria in travelers to places where infection is common. Three main medications are —mefloquine, doxycycline , or the combination of atovaquone/proguanil (*Malarone*). The